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Relationships Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Consumers' Characteristics: A Survey of the Chinese

*1. Chanthika PORNPIKAPAN; 2. Qiuling LI;
3. Joseph SY-CHANGCO; 4. Junsong CHEN

*1. Corresponding author. Associate Professor in Management, Faculty of Business Administration, University of Macau, Avenida da Universidade, Taipa, Macau, China, e-mail: ynvynv@yahoo.com; ynvynv@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-1907-8540.

2. Lecturer, School of Economics and Management, Jiangsu College of Tourism, China, e-mail: liqiuling_2006@163.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-9339-4904.

3. Assistant Professor in Marketing, Faculty of Business Administration, University of Macau, e-mail: josephs@um.edu.mo, ORCID: 0000-0002-9610-583x.

4. Dean and Professor of Marketing, School of Intelligent Finance and Business, Xi'an Jiaotong-Liverpool University, China, e-mail: junsong.chen@xjtlu.edu.cn, ORCID: 0009-0009-6322-1007.

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Abstract

Purpose: This study integrates consumer behavior models to investigate the relationships between Chinese consumers' sachet-product attitudes/behavior and personal characteristics, namely, variety seeking, frugality, value consciousness, price consciousness, personal monthly incomes, education, and household size.

Methods: A face-to-face survey is conducted with a convenience sample of 468 Chinese consumers in Shanghai and Zhuhai. The proposed relationships are analyzed by correlations and structural equation modeling.

Results: Many relationships between sachet-product attitudes/behaviors and consumer characteristics are significant as hypothesized. Variety seeking and household size positively correlate with attitudes toward products in sachets, purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and purchase and usage of products in sachets. Frugality, value consciousness, and price consciousness negatively correlate with attitudes toward products in sachets. Education negatively correlates with purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use. Personal monthly incomes negatively correlate with purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use and purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets. Finally, biological sex and age do not correlate with any of the dependent variables. Structural

equation modeling reveals that the proposed model fits the data very well in terms of Chinese consumers' sachet-product attitudes and behaviors. Specifically, higher variety seeking, larger household size, and lower personal monthly incomes lead to more-favorable attitudes toward products in sachets, which in turn induce higher purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, which in turn elicit higher purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Conclusions: Sachet marketing is profitable to companies and offers many benefits to consumers, yet there has been little investigation of the relationships between sachet-product attitudes/behaviors and consumers' characteristics. Using rigorous data analyses, this research fills this gap and provides theoretical and managerial contributions. The findings confirm the sequential linkage from attitudes → intentions → behaviors in consumer behavior theory.

Keywords: China, marketing strategy, sachet marketing, package size, sustainable consumption

Sachet marketing refers to the entire marketing strategy involving the designing, packaging, and selling a product/service in various kinds of small or mini package sizes (e.g., a small soft-paper packet, plastic bag, box, bottle, tube) at an affordable price point to consumers. Companies use products in sachets for various reasons. First, products in sachets offer an effective means to access the bottom of the pyramid market (Nulkar, 2016; Pardesi, Sharma, & Singh, 2015). Studies have indicated that low-income or low-to-middle-income countries exhibited greater acceptance of packaged or sachet products compared to developed countries (Shohrowardhy, Sohel, & Karim, 2016; Wardrop et al., 2017). For example, the Philippines witnessed the daily consumption of 163 million plastic sachets, translating to an annual consumption of 60 billion sachets (Oblea & Cabauatan, 2022). Sy-Changco, Pornpitakpan, Singh, & Bonilla (2011) unveiled that the success of sachet products in the Philippines stemmed from consumer budget constraints or lifestyle choices.

Second, products in sachets meet the daily needs of customers, even those with high income levels. For example, research found that high-income consumers were motivated to buy hair care, skin care, and personal hygiene products in sachets primarily for their ease of use, while food items were chosen for product trial purposes (Chittora & Awasthi, 2020). Moreover, the rise in sales of ready-to-eat foods correlates with the expansion of the workforce possessing substantial disposable incomes (Chaudhury, 2010; Oblea & Cabauatan, 2022). Likewise, the surge in single-person households and the overall reduction in household sizes have propelled the popularity of products in sachets across numerous Western nations (Oblea & Cabauatan, 2022). Hence, consumers have been found to like lightweight, compact bakery and snack packaging owing to its convenience, affordability, and suitability for their requirements.

Third, sachet marketing is also a tool to reach people who can afford the regular size. Companies often tailor single-serve sachets to cater to the specific preferences of high-income individuals, allowing for the customization of product offerings based on serving size. For instance, Chittora and Awasthi (2020) found that products in sachets, such as biscuits, snacks, and coffee, were frequently perceived as staple goods among consumers who made regular purchases. Correspondingly, research conducted by Jambeck et al. (2024) revealed that a significant portion of candy and personal care items, approximately 75% and 63% respectively, were commonly packaged in multilayer plastic or clear film, including sachets. Intriguingly, consumer behavior studies have shown a preference for smaller portion sizes (under 100 grams) in delivering popular products, as opposed to larger sizes (Kulkarni, 2019).

The practice of selling products in sachets has become a strategic marketing strategy employed by not only small firms but also multinational companies (Oblea & Cabauatan, 2022). Products in sachets have been offered by consumer goods companies for decades to penetrate the low-income market and bolster sales (Kandpal, 2015; Singh, Ang, & Sy-Changco,

2009). Within some multinational corporations, fast-moving consumer goods are distributed to low-income and below-the-poverty-line segments as part of their experimental strategies. For instance, to deliver something new to their customers in terms of value and quality, fast-moving consumer goods companies were found to test their products frequently, resulting in sachet packaging having a large market share through promotion (Mehra & Singh, 2016). Although these sachets do not represent the most economical way to buy goods, consumers appreciate their affordability (Anderson, 2006).

In short, sachet marketing creates an opportunity to deliver different sizes of products and services to suit consumers' needs, thus increasing sales, generating profits, and ensuring the sustainability of a company. Given the widespread utilization of sachets in certain countries with sizable populations, the success of these products has become evident and integral to consumers' daily lives.

With a population of about 1.417 billion as of February 2025 according to the live update of www.worldometers.info/world-population/china-population, China has been the world's second-largest economy by gross domestic product since 2010 (International Trade Administration, 2023). If companies can raise the popularity of products in sachets in the huge China market, they will benefit from the increased sales and profits while also delivering many advantages to consumers as discussed above. To achieve this, it is critical to understand Chinese consumers' attitudes and purchase/usage behaviors with respect to products in sachets; however, scanty empirical evidence is available regarding this (Ohlwein, 2022). To address this research gap, this study investigates the relationships between sachet-product attitudes/behaviors and consumers' personal characteristics, including relevant demographic factors and personality traits. Moreover, research indicates that attitudes towards objects stem from beliefs, perceptions, and knowledge concerning them (Patel & Bhatt, 2015; Shirai & Satomura, 2021; Sy-changco et al., 2011). For instance, Steinmann et al. (2019) investigated how product-related factors, such as information displayed on packaging, package size, and product price, influenced self-regulation. The findings revealed that consumers perceived dosage control as pivotal in their sachet-product consumption patterns. Forming implementation intentions as a self-regulatory strategy may aid consumers in enhancing their decision-making processes and translating them into action (Gollwitzer & Sheeran, 2009). Consequently, understanding these intricate relationships between attitudes/behaviors towards sachet products and consumer characteristics will assist marketers in devising marketing strategies for sachet products in China. It also provides theoretical contributions with respect to models of consumer behavior.

The following sections present (i) hypotheses derived from a review of the current literature pertaining to the above relationships, (ii) methods of an empirical study to test the hypotheses, (iii) results, and (iv) discussions of the research contributions, managerial suggestions, and future-research suggestions.

Literature Review

Determinants of Purchase/Usage Frequency of Products in Sachets

According to the two consumer behavior models in Kotler and Armstrong (2021), buyer responses are influenced by a complex set of external and internal factors. Known as the blackbox model, *the environment factors* include the marketing stimuli (consisting of product, price, place, and promotion), economic, technological, social, and cultural factors. These environment factors affect *the buyer's blackbox* (consisting of the buyer's characteristics and decision process), which in turn affects *buyer responses* (consisting of buying attitudes and preferences; purchase behavior that includes what, when, where, and how much the buyer buys; brand engagement and relationships). Consistent with this, previous research found that product attributes (e.g., perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use) were important

drivers of Chinese consumers' attitudes toward home-used consumptions (Qi, Yu, & Ploeger, 2020).

In addition, another model outlines more-specific factors that influence buyer behavior, namely, (i) cultural factors (consisting of culture, subculture, social class); (ii) social factors (consisting of groups and social networks, family, role and status); (iii) personal factors (consisting of age and life-cycle stage, occupation, economic situation, lifestyle, personality and self-concept); and (iv) psychological factors (consisting of motivation, perception, learning, beliefs and attitudes). Research found that cultural values, norms, and external contextual factors bore on consumers' perceived value of a product or service, which refers to the ratio of the perceived benefits of the good or service to the perceived sacrifice incurred to acquire it. A higher perceived value of a product was found to strengthen consumers' purchase intentions (Petrick, 2004). Finally, theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1985) posits that people's attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence their behavioral intentions.

Apparently, these useful, reasonable, and widely used models of consumer behaviors are not all-inclusive, and myriad other factors and sub-factors may be added to provide a better and deeper understanding of consumers. It is not possible either for any study to examine all the factors in the above models. Therefore, this study develops an integrated framework by extracting variables from the theory of planned behavior model (Ajzen, 1985) and the above two models (Kotler & Armstrong, 2021) to explain Chinese consumers' acceptance of products in sachets as shown in Figure 1. The rationales for the proposed relationships are presented next.

Figure 1

A Proposed Conceptual Model to Explain Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors

Relationships Between Attitudes and Behaviors

This study investigates the following key dependent variables in marketing. The first is *attitudes toward products in sachets*. The second is *purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use*. Purchase intentions refer to an individual's motivation and willingness to buy products or services. It should be taken note that this study focuses on purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, not for business use or other venues such as gyms, camps, and hotels, where it is common to use small packages. Finally, this study also measures consumers' real behavior in terms of *purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets*.

Theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1985) suggests that consumers' attitudes directly affect their behavioral intentions, which will in turn affect purchase behaviors. Attitudes can be viewed as personal traits influencing subsequent behaviors (Mitchell & Olson, 1981; Richard & Chebat, 2016). Moreover, previous research has unveiled a strong positive relationship between attitudes and purchase intentions toward the products. For example, Liang and Lim (2011) found that consumers' attitudes toward online food purchase significantly and positively influenced their buying intentions. Based on the above theory and empirical evidence, it is hypothesized as follows:

H1. Positive relationships exist between attitudes toward products in sachets, purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets. Specifically, the model in Figure 1 proposes that attitudes toward products in sachets affect purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, which in turn affect purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Influences of Personality Traits

Theory of planned behavior states that opportunities and resources, such as the accessibility of products, may affect purchase behaviors. It also emphasizes the impact of subjective norms and volitional control on purchase behaviors. By integrating theory of planned behavior with the two models presented in Kotler and Armstrong (2021) discussed above, this study proposes that certain personal characteristics (i.e., personality traits and demographic characteristics) serve as drivers of consumers' attitudes toward products in sachets, which in turn stimulate purchase intentions toward products in sachets. Specifically, this study focuses on variety seeking, frugality, value consciousness, price consciousness, personal monthly income, education, and household size to explain consumer sachet-product behaviors.

Relationships Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Variety Seeking

Variety-seeking consumers are particularly inclined towards products with low purchase risks (Phau & Teah, 2009). The low price of products in sachets is therefore well suited for satisfying consumers' curiosity and need for experimentation with various products. Products in sachets enable consumers to spread the money across a wide range of items and facilitate trials by non-users and consumers who may want to switch to other brands.

As for Chinese consumers' variety seeking behaviors, the economic reforms in China have brought about a rising demand for diversified products (Cui & Liu, 2001). The markets have become increasingly fragmented, and consumers want greater varieties that suit their diverging needs and aspirations than before. In addition, variety seeking might satisfy a desire for group affiliation (McAlister & Pessemier, 1982), which is important in a Confucian culture like China. More important, variety-seeking inclinations influence consumers' readiness to

buy products or services (Wei, 1997). These rationales and empirical evidence lead to the following hypothesis:

H2: Positive relationships exist between variety seeking and (2a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (2b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (2c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Relationships Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Frugality, Value Consciousness, and Price Consciousness

Previous research has revealed that despite modernization, many traditional values are vital in influencing product consumption (Hofstede & Bond, 1988; Wei, 1997), and the Confucian culture is a key factor to explain many Chinese behaviors (Wong & Ahuvia, 1998). One aspect of Confucianism—frugality or emphasis on avoiding waste—is particularly relevant to product consumption. China consistently has a high savings rate, with a gross savings rate of 45.9% in 2021 (CEIC Data, 2023). On one hand, products in sachets seem to fit the value of frugality in that people are able to spend less per purchase compared to buying products in larger packages. In addition, according to the experiment results in Pornpitakpan (2010), people used less amount per consumption when the product was in a smaller package. On the other hand, frugality does not mean that consumers consider only the affordable pricing aspect. Instead, the concept of frugality revolves around the idea that there is a multidimensional understanding of affordability that accounts for financial, societal, infrastructure, and ecological affordability (Herstatt & Tiwari, 2020). Although products in sachets seem to contribute to financial well-being, they raise significant environmental concerns such as public health and standard of living because of the large amounts of plastic waste and littering (Lim, 2022). Frugality is often related with a focus on social sustainability that highlights responsible consumption and reduction of unnecessary waste. The disposable nature of sachets may be perceived as contradictory to the principles of frugality. Therefore, it is hypothesized as follows:

H3: Negative relationships exist between frugality and (3a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (3b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (3c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Next, value consciousness influences consumers' readiness to buy products or services (Wei, 1997). Products in sachets are likely to be regarded as providing rather poor value for money due to their typically higher price per volume compared to that of products in regular packages. Thus, it is hypothesized as follows:

H4: Negative relationships exist between value consciousness and (4a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (4b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (4c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Finally, price sensitiveness influences consumers' readiness to buy products or services (Rachmawati & Muflikhati, 2017; Wei, 1997). A related concept is *price consciousness*, which refers to the extent to which consumers are anxious about paying low prices (Lichtenstein, Ridgway, & Netemeyer, 1993). Researchers concluded that price or affordability exerted the greatest influence on consumers' decisions to purchase sachets (Chittora & Awasthi, 2020; Pardesi et al, 2015; Phau & Teah, 2009; Rachmawati & Muflikhati, 2017). Consumers are aware of sachet products' price advantage. Consequently, individuals with lower incomes or those self-identifying as more impoverished tended to procure sachets in greater quantities to fulfill their daily requirements (Anderson & Billou, 2007; Jaiswal & Gupta, 2015; Patel & Bhatt, 2015). Yet, low prices per se may not be attractive if they essentially mean high prices per volume, which is usually the case for products in sachets. In other words, the seemingly low prices of products in sachets are not actually cheap in the eyes of most consumers. Petit, Lunardo, and Rickard (2020) found that consumers showed a stronger preference for large food packages over small ones due to their lower per-unit costs, resulting in monetary savings. Previous

research has shown that Chinese consumers are value conscious and price sensitive (Cui & Liu, 2001). The popularity of *shanzhai* products (i.e., products emerging from an imitation of another product but with its own brand name) was found to underscore how their combination of affordability and quality significantly impacted Chinese consumers' buying choices (Chen & Wang, 2021). Stemming from the above discussions and empirical evidence, H5 predicts the following:

H5: Negative relationships exist between price consciousness and (5a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (5b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (5c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Influences of Demographic Characteristics

This section discusses the relationships between sachet-product attitudes/behaviors and demographic variables that are important and frequently used in marketing planning, namely biological sex, age, household size, education, and incomes.

Relationships Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Biological Sex

Research found that women liked to shop on traditional shopping sites that enabled them to establish interactions with others. In contrast, men emphasized shopping convenience and time saving more than did women (Rodgers & Harris, 2003). It can be derived from the above findings that products in sachets are likely to fulfill the needs of both genders. Female consumers, who generally enjoy the shopping process, should be happy because small packages require more frequent visits to physical stores than do large packages. In this context, they have opportunities to chat and to share information with other consumers in the stores. For male consumers, who tend to emphasize convenience and time saving, products in sachets can be good substitutes for products in larger packages because sachets are easy to use and carry. In addition, some research has indicated that the gender gap in products and services purchasing behaviors is disappearing (Luan, Fung, & Atan, 2008). According to the aforementioned discussions, H6 predicts the following:

H6: No relationships exist between biological sex and (6a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (6b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (6c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Relationships Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Age

Age has lost its power in predicting consumers' attitudes and behaviors (Guido, Amatulli, & Peluso, 2014). Instead, researchers are in favor of other dimensions of age, that is, the cognitive age, which according to Barak (2009), refers to the subjective perception of how old one feels. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7: No relationships exist between age and (7a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (7b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (7c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Relationships Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Household Size

Consumers' household size (i.e., the number of persons living in the household) may positively affect their purchasing behaviors of products in sachets. First, research has investigated the relationship between consumption and household size (Annuziata, Mariani, & Vecchio, 2019; Kumar et al, 2021). For example, by utilizing household size to estimate the quantity of goods consumed, research found that household size positively influenced consumption expenditures (Kiran & Dhawan, 2015; Wardrop et al, 2017). Besides, it was found

that bigger families went for shopping more frequently than did smaller ones (Wang et al., 2013). More time spent in shopping should increase consumers' exposure to information about different brands and sachet packages, thus promoting intentions to try and purchase products in sachets.

Second, products in sachets are compatible with interdependent relationships among Chinese people. China has been identified as a country with an interdependent culture (as opposed to an independent one), which reflects that the construal of self depends on self and the relationship with one's family, relatives, kinship clan, and so forth (Hofstede, Hofstede, & Minkov, 2010). Individuals may differ in their preferences but also consider others' interests to yield social benefits. Therefore, Chinese people living in a big household may want to buy products in sachets, which allow people to buy many product variants at a low price, to satisfy a wide range of family members' tastes and interests. These rationales lead to the following hypothesis:

H8: Positive relationships exist between household size and (8a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (8b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (8c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Relationships Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Education

A positive relationship was found between education and the search for information regarding environmental problems, which in turn brought about new consumption markets (Ritter et al., 2015). Accordingly, the functional and economic aspects of products such as price may not be the priority for these people in making purchase decisions (Wang, Liu, & Qi, 2014). Because discarded sachets usually end up as trash in landfills, the harmful outcomes of sachets on the environment may be more salient in the views of high-educated Chinese people than in the views of low-educated ones. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H9: Negative relationships exist between education and (9a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (9b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (9c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Relationships Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Personal Monthly Incomes

It has been found that monthly incomes have significant influences on product purchase decisions (Liu, Pieniak, & Verbeke, 2014). Most Chinese employees get their payment on a monthly basis, so they generally can afford products in regular sizes. Besides, research has shown that compared with consumers with low incomes, Chinese consumers with relatively high incomes pay more attention to product information and express more dependence on all sources of information (Cheng et al., 2016). It is therefore likely that high-income people are more exposed to the non-environment-friendly information of sachets than are low-income people and thus less interested in products in sachets. All these rationales lead to the following hypothesis:

H10: Negative relationships exist between personal monthly incomes and (10a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (10b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (10c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

Method

Research Design

This research uses a survey to collect data and employs correlation and structural equation modeling to analyze the relationships between sachet attitudes/behaviors and personal characteristics of the Chinese in China.

Sample and Data Collection Procedure

Through convenience sampling at shopping malls and universities, respondents in two cities of China differing in size, development, and income, namely Zhuhai (Tier 3 city) and Shanghai (Tier 1 city), were invited on a face-to-face basis to answer Chinese questionnaires in as much time as they needed. A face-to-face survey secures higher response rates compared with other methods such as phone or online surveys because the presence of researchers could encourage participation and help build trust, leading to increased cooperation from respondents. Besides, it allows researchers to clarify questions, ensuring accurate data collection. As for the city tiers in China, factors such as population size, economic development, infrastructure, and administrative significance are commonly used to determine the tiers that reflect their economic development and urbanization. Tier 1 cities such as Shanghai, Beijing, Guangzhou, and Shenzhen have over US\$300 billion gross domestic products and over 15 million people, while Tier 3 cities such as Zhuhai, Guilin, Guiyang, and Nanning have US\$18–67 billion gross domestic products and 150,000–3,000,000 people (Wong, 2019).

After unusable questionnaires were excluded, participants consisted of 468 Chinese adults (161 from Zhuhai, 307 from Shanghai). The sample characteristics were as follows: 229 (48.9%) were male, the average age was 31.57 years ($SD = 9.145$), the average years of education were 15.674 ($SD = 2.327$), and the average personal monthly incomes were RMB 9,652.78 ($SD = 8,039.96$). All of the participants were born and raised in China and had never lived outside China for more than five years.

Measures

Sachet Attitudes/Behaviors

Four dependent variables are of focal interest in this study. First, adapted from Aaker and Williams (1998) attitudes toward the brand scale, the **attitudes toward products in sachets** consisted of three items asking: “To me, products in sachets are...” with responses anchored by 1 (*Very bad*) to 7 (*Very good*), 1 (*Not likable at all*) to 7 (*Very likable*), and 1 (*Very undesirable*) to 7 (*Very desirable*). Second, the **purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use** asked: “For your use at home, how likely is it that you will buy products in sachets if they are available in the stores where you always buy things?” with responses anchored by 1 (*Very unlikely*) to 7 (*Very likely*). Finally, **purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets** consisted of two items: (i) the **purchase frequency of products in sachets** asked: “On average, how often did you buy products in sachets during the past one year?” with responses anchored by 1 (*Did not buy at all*) to 7 (*Bought very often*); and (ii) the **usage frequency of products in sachets** asked: “On average, how often did you use products in sachets during the past one year?” with responses anchored by 1 (*Did not use at all*) to 7 (*Used very often*).

Personality Traits

The following personality scales were 7-point Likert scales, and the items selected were based on the confirmatory factor analyses elaborated in Table 1. First, the scale of **variety-seeking tendency** was adapted from Donthu and Gilliland (1996), namely, (i) I like to try different things; (ii) I like a great deal of variety; and (iii) I like new and different styles. Second, the scale of **frugality** was adapted from Lastovicka et al. (1999), namely, (i) If you can re-use an item you already have, there's no sense in buying something new; (ii) I believe in being careful in how I spend my money; and (iii) I discipline myself to get the most from my money. Third, the scale of **value consciousness** was adapted from Lichtenstein, Netemeyer, and Burton (1990), namely, (i) I am very concerned about low prices, but I am equally concerned about product quality; (ii) When grocery shopping, I compare the prices of different brands to be sure I get the best value for the money; (iii) When purchasing a product, I always try to maximize the quality I get for the money I spend; and (iv) When I buy products, I like to be sure that I am getting my money's worth. Finally, the scale of **price consciousness** was adapted from Lichtenstein et al. (1993), namely, (i) The money saved by finding lower prices is usually not worth the time and effort; (ii) I would never shop at more than one store to find low prices; and (iii) The time it takes to find low prices is usually not worth the effort. All these three items were reverse-coded so that higher scores indicate higher price consciousness.

Table 1
Reliability and Validity of Latent Constructs (N = 468)

Construct	Number of Items in the Scale	Item Reliability Standardized Estimate	Composite Reliability CR	Convergent Validity Average Variance Extracted	Discriminant Validity						
					1	2	3	4	5	6	
1. Variety seeking	3	0.804-0.840	0.864	0.679	0.824						
2. Frugality	3	0.589-0.806	0.768	0.529	0.050	0.727					
3. Value consciousness	4	0.600-0.835	0.806	0.514	0.228	0.620	0.717				
4. Price consciousness	3	0.721-0.843	0.832	0.555	-0.123	-0.034	0.126	0.745			
5. Attitudes toward products in sachets	3	0.835-0.912	0.893	0.678	0.156	-0.129	-0.098	-0.124	0.823		
6. Purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets	2	0.850-0.922	0.880	0.786	0.124	0.088	0.007	-0.011	0.605	0.887	

Note. To examine the convergent and discriminant validity of the multi-item scales, this study follows standard procedures of performing confirmatory factor analyses using Mplus 8.0 (Muthén & Muthén, 2017). The results in this table indicate that all the multi-item scales conform to prescribed values for item reliability, composite reliability, average variance extracted, and discriminant validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Thus, the multi-item scales have adequate psychometric properties in terms of composite reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. All standardized estimates are significant at $p < .001$ (two-tailed). Discriminant validity results are on the diagonal in bold.

Results

Correlation Analyses

Table 2 shows correlations between the variables to test the hypotheses.

Table 2

Correlation Between Sachet-Product Attitudes/Behaviors and Personal Characteristics

Variable	Correlation	Attitudes Toward Products in Sachets	Purchase Intentions Toward Products in Sachets for Home Use	Purchase/Usage Frequency of Products in Sachets
Attitudes toward products in sachets	<i>r</i>	1	.517***	.542***
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)		.000	.000
Purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use	<i>r</i>	.517***	1	.599***
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.000		.000
Purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets	<i>r</i>	.542***	.599***	1
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.000	.000	
Variety seeking	<i>r</i>	.144**	.081*	.100*
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.001	.039	.015
Frugality	<i>r</i>	-.120**	-.0034	.059
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.005	.474	.101
Value consciousness	<i>r</i>	-.085*	-.039	.011
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.034	.200	.410
Price consciousness	<i>r</i>	-.101*	-.031	-.001
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.015	.252	.488
Biological sex#	<i>r</i>	.076	-.049	-.011
	<i>p</i> (2-tailed)	.099	.292	.804
Age#	<i>r</i>	-.006	-.006	-.054
	<i>p</i> (2-tailed)	.889	.901	.242
Household size	<i>r</i>	.117**	.205***	.179***
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.006	.000	.000
Years of education	<i>r</i>	.038	-.151**	-.047
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.207	.001	.156
Personal monthly incomes	<i>r</i>	-.050	-.153***	-.159***
	<i>p</i> (1-tailed)	.139	.000	.000

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

All the tests except for biological sex and age are one-tailed tests because of the directional hypotheses that hypothesize either positive or negative relationships.

As predicted in H1, attitudes toward products in sachets, purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets are positively correlated, with r coefficients ranging from .517 to .599 ($p < .001$). Variety seeking positively correlates with attitudes toward products in sachets ($r = .144$, $p = .001$), purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use ($r = .081$, $p = .039$), and purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets ($r = .1$, $p = .015$), supporting Hypotheses 2a, 2b, and 2c, respectively. Frugality negatively correlates with attitudes toward products in sachets ($r = -.12$, $p = .005$), supporting H3a. Similarly, value consciousness negatively correlates with attitudes toward products in sachets ($r = -.085$, $p = .034$), supporting H4a. Consistent with H5a, price consciousness negatively correlates with attitudes toward products in sachets ($r = -.101$, $p = .015$).

In support of H6 and H7, sex and age do not correlate with any of the dependent variables. Household size positively correlates with attitudes toward products in sachets ($r = .117, p = .006$), purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use ($r = .205, p = .000$), and purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets ($r = .179, p = .000$), supporting H8a, H8b, and H8c, respectively. Consistent with H9b, education negatively correlates with purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use ($r = -.151, p = .001$). Similarly, in accordance with H10b and H10c, personal monthly incomes negatively correlate with purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use ($r = -.153, p = .000$) and purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets ($r = -.159, p = .000$). Table 3 summarizes the hypothesis testing results based on correlations.

Table 3

Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results Based on Correlations

Hypothesis	Result
H1: + correlation between attitudes toward products in sachets, purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported.
H2: + correlation between variety seeking and (2a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (2b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (2c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 2a, 2b, and 2c.
H3: - correlation between frugality and (3a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (3b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (3c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 3a.
H4: - correlation between value consciousness and (4a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (4b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (4c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 4a.
H5: - correlation between price consciousness and (5a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (5b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (5c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 5a.
H6: No correlation between biological sex and (6a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (6b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (6c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 6a, 6b, and 6c.
H7: No correlation between age and (7a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (7b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (7c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 7a, 7b, and 7c.
H8: + correlation between household size and (8a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (8b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (8c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 8a, 8b, and 8c.
H9: - correlation between education and (9a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (9b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and (9c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 9b.
H10: - correlation between personal monthly incomes and (10a) attitudes toward products in sachets, (10b) purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, (10c) purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.	Supported for 10b, and 10c.

Structural Equation Modeling Analyses

The proposed model in Figure 1 is estimated by Mplus 8.0 (Muthén & Muthén, 2017), and the latent variables, their indicators, and standardized path coefficients are shown in Figure 2. The results show that the proposed model provides a good fit to the data (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) as indicated by $\chi^2(197) = 445.383$, $p < .001$ (χ^2 of 445.383 divided by df of 197 equals 2.26, which is under 3); root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) = 0.052; comparative fit index (CFI) = 0.941; Tucker–Lewis index (TLI) = 0.931; and standardized root mean squared residual (SRMR) = 0.060. These results support the effect of consumers' characteristics on purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets. Specifically, variety seeking has the highest impact (standardized path coefficient = .145, $p < .05$), followed by household size (standardized path coefficient = .121, $p < .05$), and personal monthly incomes (standardized path coefficient = -.079, $p < .05$), on attitudes toward products in sachets, which in turn influence purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use (standardized path coefficient = .548, $p < .05$), which in turn affect purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets (standardized path coefficient = .637, $p < .05$). In other words, attitudes toward products in sachets and purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use mediate the effect of consumers' characteristics on purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets. Taken together, the findings confirm the sequential linkage from attitudes → intentions → behaviors in consumer behavior theory.

Discussion

Theoretical Contributions of the Study

This study surveys 468 Chinese residents to achieve the following contributions: (i) providing in-depth quantitative analyses of the relationships between sachet-product attitudes/behaviors and personal characteristics (personality traits and demographic variables) of the Chinese in China; (ii) offering managerial advice for planning and selling products in sachets in China markets; and (iii) suggesting future research in this area. Ten hypotheses are derived from theories and empirical evidence, and most of them are supported. This study develops an integrated theoretical framework that extracts variables from the theory of planned behavior and two consumer behavior models. The structural equation model results verify the proposed causal role of consumers' characteristics on purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

With respect to theory of planned behavior, attitudes toward products in sachets are found to have a significant positive effect on Chinese consumers' purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, which in turn affect purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets. These results are consistent with previous research involving consumers' product acceptance (Qi & Ploeger, 2019; Yadav & Pathak, 2016). As for the integrated theoretical model, the results support the findings from studies related to the influence of consumers' characteristics on consumption behaviors (Liu et al., 2014; Qi et al., 2020) and show that (i) consumers' characteristics influence attitudes toward products in sachets and purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, and that (ii) these two variables serve as a mediational mechanism through which consumers' characteristics affect purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets. In particular, higher variety seeking, larger household size, and lower personal monthly incomes lead to more-favorable attitudes toward products in sachets, which in turn induce higher purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use, which in turn result in higher purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets. Nevertheless, as predicted, biological sex and age do not correlate with sachet-product attitudes and behaviors.

Figure 2

Structural Equation Modeling of the Model in Figure 1 Portrayed with Indicators and Standardized Path Coefficients

Note. The numbers on the arrows refer to standardized path coefficients. All standardized path coefficients are significant at $p < .05$ except the ones marked with ns.

iv1 = variety-seeking tendency.

iv11 = I like to try different things.

iv12 = I like a great deal of variety.

iv13 = I like new and different styles.

iv2 = frugality.

iv24 = If you can re-use an item you already have, there's no sense in buying something new.

iv25 = I believe in being careful in how I spend my money.

iv26 = I discipline myself to get the most from my money.

iv3 = value consciousness.

iv31 = I am very concerned about low prices, but I am equally concerned about product quality.

iv32 = When grocery shopping, I compare the prices of different brands to be sure I get the best value for the money.

iv33 = When purchasing a product, I always try to maximize the quality I get for the money I spend.

iv34 = When I buy products, I like to be sure that I am getting my money's worth.

iv4 = price consciousness.

iv43 = The money saved by finding lower prices is usually not worth the time and effort (reverse-coded).

iv44 = I would never shop at more than one store to find low prices (reverse-coded).

iv45 = The time it takes to find low prices is usually not worth the effort (reverse-coded).

iv5b = personal monthly incomes.

iv6 = education.

iv7 = household size.

m1 = attitudes toward products in sachets.

m11 = To me, products in sachets are ... from 1 (Very bad) to 7 (Very good).

m12 = To me, products in sachets are ... from 1 (Not likable at all) to 7 (Very likable).

m13 = To me, products in sachets are ... from 1 (Very undesirable) to 7 (Very desirable).

m2 = purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use.

dv = purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets.

dv1 = purchase frequency of products in sachets.

dv2 = usage frequency of products in sachets.

Accordingly, this study can benefit future researchers who explore the topic of products in sachets and consumer preferences. In relevance to consumer theory, individuals have the right to choose from the options of goods and services available, and the choice is influenced by many factors, such as budget constraints, supply, and personal preferences. In this study, both the economic and non-economic factors are found to be associated with the decision of Chinese people to consume products in sachets. The affordability of products in sachets is not the only reason why Chinese consumers purchase them since non-economic factors (i.e., variety seeking and household size) are also influencing their purchasing behavior. The low unit price of products in sachets allows Chinese consumers to seek variety easily and to elevate themselves by using global brands that are made affordable in small packages. Products in sachets also fit the Chinese's interdependence and collectivism, as evidenced by the acceptance of products in sachets by big households. Because products in sachets are cost-effective, one can satisfy the preferences of every household member, buy products individually, and control household budgets. Thus, this study provides an additional contribution to the knowledge regarding the sachet phenomenon and Chinese culture through the examination of consumer attitudes/behaviors toward products in sachets.

In summary, this study extends research on Chinese consumption behaviors by investigating the impact of consumers' characteristics on sachet-product attitudes and behaviors. The findings suggest that the divergent effects of consumers' characteristics on their purchase/usage frequency of products in sachets are mediated by attitudes toward products in sachets and purchase intentions toward products in sachets for home use.

Managerial Suggestions

Based on the empirical findings of this study, the following suggestions are provided to increase consumers' acceptance and usage of products in sachets. First, businesses can tailor their marketing perspectives and strategies regarding products in sachets to accommodate the needs of all classes of consumers more comprehensively. Contrary to the claim that products in sachets exclusively cater to the underprivileged, consumption of products in sachets in China is spread across different income classes to fulfill Chinese consumers' variety-seeking needs and accommodate households with many members. Hence, manufacturers and retailers must determine the appropriate sizes for each product and consider assortment and package size decisions together.

Second, companies should make sure that minimal discrepancy exists between the pricing of products in sachets and the pricing of their counterparts in larger packages, especially in terms of price per gram or milliliter. During turbulent economic periods, such as recessions, price reductions and downsizing of packages may be an effective marketing strategy. For example, a study by Li et al. (2023) unveiled that the COVID-19 pandemic greatly impacted China's labor market and China experienced a pronounced increase in unemployment rate. The findings of this study underscore that lower personal incomes are associated with the advantageous utilization of products in sachets. Thus, marketing is crucial to the success of the sachet economy by convincing consumers of its favorable value proposition.

Third, in China, where consumers desire product variety, products in sachets serve as a means to explore new functionalities and innovations. Sachet-packaged products offer companies opportunities for both disruptive and incremental innovations. Product attributes significantly influence product choices, especially among the younger generation of consumers. Therefore, marketers and retailers must offer various package sizes of a particular product to enhance effectiveness. Providing small-sized packages with multiple variants or flavors can effectively meet consumers' preferences.

Fourth, products in sachets, like other goods and services, are marketed to appeal to consumers. Companies may increase expenditures on marketing communications and sales

promotions to build brand image and increase awareness and demand of products in sachets. Marketers and retailers should promote the benefits of sachet packages over larger packages. For example, marketers should emphasize that products in sachets are fresh, convenient to carry and use, hygienic, easy to control the product usage amount, and economical.

Finally, the insights gained from this study about the relationships between sachet-product attitudes/behaviors and consumers' characteristics (in particular, personality traits and demographic variables) enhance the theoretical and empirical foundation for segmentation, targeting, and positioning strategies in selling products in sachets.

Suggestions for Future Research

Future research may include more cities/towns in China to enrich the understanding of the China markets. Local market disparities in China are persistent and in some cases have grown more pronounced. Discrepant incomes, various local subcultures and lifestyles, and diverse consumption patterns result in different levels of consumer readiness and responsiveness to marketing efforts. Thus, systematic research in more cities/towns will help formulate new-product introduction and existing-product expansion strategies and overcome the hidden barriers between regions.

Future research may also focus on the dynamics of consumer characteristics to come up with a proper social matrix for studying sachet-product attitudes/behaviors of the Chinese. Examining the distinctive characteristics of consumers in various regions can help generalize a parsimonious profile for Chinese consumers with respect to sachet-product attitudes/behaviors and can help companies determine the appropriate target markets for products in sachets. In addition, future research may replicate this study in other countries to investigate whether cross-cultural differences exist in the relationships between the variables examined in this study.

Theoretically, experiments can be conducted to investigate whether an endorsement from message sources perceived to be high in credibility (see review by Pornpitakpan, 2004b) and attractiveness (see review by Pornpitakpan, Li, & Fu, 2017) and primed or induced personality traits, as opposed to natural personality traits, of consumers, can affect sachet-product attitudes and behaviors. For example, people can be primed to be fond of variety seeking and to be frugal, value-conscious, and price-conscious. If such causal relationships are confirmed, the results can suggest many marketing strategies to promote products in sachets. Moreover, research has found that consumers' circadian arousal and time of day influence consumer attitudes and behaviors (e.g., Gullo et al., 2019; Pornpitakpan, 2004a), future studies may thus examine the impact of time of day and consumer morningness–eveningness (see Caci et al., 2005; Pornpitakpan, 1998, 2000; and Pornpitakpan, Yue, & Fu, 2025 for the validation of morningness–eveningness measures on respondents from several countries such as China and Thailand) on attitudes and purchase intentions toward products in sachets.

In addition, future research may identify additional predictors and determinants of sachet-product attitudes/behaviors. These may include, for instance, consumers' materialism, vanity, venturesomeness, self-monitoring, future orientation, and health consciousness. Apart from studying the reasons for sachet preferences among individuals across various income brackets, further analysis is possible for sachet preferences within each product category. Finally, mini packaging of service-oriented products, such as mobile data plans and talk time, may reveal distinct consumer behaviors.

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